

Formation of Heterocyclic Compounds from Thioacetylcarbamic Acid Derivatives. Part I.

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This paper describes experiments on the action of hydrazines and diamines on dicarbethoxythioacetylcarbamic acid (A), carbethoxyaceto-thioacetylcarbamic acid (B) and diacetylthioacetocarbamic acid (C) (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1933, **16A**, 107).

The above compounds which bear a close resemblance to acetylurethane react readily in the cold with amines and hydrazines with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen. The fact that these compounds are much more reactive towards basic compounds than acetylurethane (*cf.* Ghosh and Betrabet, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 899) is explained on the basis that sulphur is more acidic than oxygen, as is evinced by a comparison of the mercaptans with the alcohols. In this connection reference is made to the great reactivity of thioketonic esters (Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 472).

An 1 : 2 : 4-triazole derivative (I) is obtained by reacting the compound (A) with phenylhydrazine, the reaction taking the following course :

The formula assigned to (I) is established by the analytical data and by the fact that the compound is insoluble in cold alkali and does not decolourise bromine water. On hydrolysis it yields the mono-acid (II) which, on decarboxylation, yields the compound (III). In this connection reference may be made to the work of Ghosh and Betrabet (*loc. cit.*) on the synthesis of 1 : 2 : 4-triazole derivatives from acetylurethane and hydrazines.

The compound (B) reacts with phenylhydrazine to yield a pyrazolone derivative (IV). That the carboxyl group in this compound is firmly attached to the nitrogen atom is shown by the fact that carbon dioxide is not eliminated by heating the compound with even 10 % alcoholic potash.

With hydrazine hydrate the compound (A) yields a pyrazolone derivative (V) (*cf.* Worrall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 3092, on the action of hydrazine hydrate on dicarbethoxythioacetanilide) which, on hydrolysis, yields the mono-acid (VI). The compound (VI) is stable towards alkali and reacts with benzaldehyde to give the compound (VII), confirming thereby the presence of an active methylene group.

The compound (C), unlike (A), gives with hydrazine hydrate not a pyrazolone but a triazole derivative (VIII) which is hydrolysed by alkali to yield the compound (IX).

4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide and the compound (A) react to form a thioheptadiazine derivative (X), (Xa) being postulated as an intermediate (*cf.* De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **3**, 31; Ghosh and Betrabet, *loc. cit.*). The compound (X) is not desulphurised by mercuric oxide indicating that the sulphur atom is cyclic; with acetic anhydride it decomposes into phenyl isothiocyanate and a tarry product.

The compound (A) reacts with *o*-phenylene diamine to yield a benzimidazole derivative (XI), the reaction taking the following course.

(XII)

On hydrolysis the compound (XI) yields 2-methylbenzimidazole (XII) (Hübner, *Annalen*, 1881, 209, 353); this reaction confirms the assigned constitution. The compound (C) with *o*-phenylenediamine gives similarly the benzimidazole derivative (XIII) and the compound (A) likewise with ethylenediamine gives the imidazole derivative (XIV).

(XIII)

(XIV)

In connection with the synthesis of imidazole derivatives, mention should be made that many substances containing the imidazole group are formed in the metabolic processes of the living organism. Histamine (β -iminazoylethylamine) possesses pronounced physiological activity.

From the reactions studied above, it is observed that thioacetyl-carbamic acid derivatives are characterised by their pronounced reactivity and as such are of considerable value for synthetic purposes. The general mechanism of the above reactions is that sulphuretted hydrogen is first eliminated and then ring-closure is effected by the elimination of either alcohol or water.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dicarbethoxythioacetylcarbamic acid (A), *Carbethoxyacetothioacetylcarbamic acid* (B) and *Diacetylthioacetocarabamic acid* (C) were prepared according to the method of Ghosh and Guha (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1933, 16A, 111).

3-Keto-2-phenyl-5-dicarbethoxymethyl-dihydro-1:2:4-triazole (I).—Phenylhydrazine (2.2 g.) was added to an alcoholic solution of the compound (A) (5.3 g.) when the reaction immediately commenced with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen and rise in temperature. For completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for about an hour and on cooling, a crystalline solid was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in colourless shining rectangular plates, m.p. 203°, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 56.11; H, 5.75; N, 12.98. $C_{15}H_{17}O_5N_3$ requires C, 56.42; H, 5.33; N, 13.17 per cent). It does not decolourise bromine water and is insoluble in cold dilute alkali.

3-Keto-2-phenyl-dihydro-1:2:4-triazole-5-acetic acid (II).—The above compound (I, 2 g.) was heated on the water-bath with excess of 15% alcoholic potash for about 5 hours, when the alcohol was distilled under reduced pressure. The dried mass was treated with cold water and acidified slowly with acetic acid when there was evolution of carbon dioxide. The solid was purified by dissolving in aqueous bicarbonate and acidification with acetic acid. The product was crystallised from alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. above 300° (turning dark at 280°), yield 0.8 g. (Found: N, 19.01. $C_{10}H_9O_3N_3$ requires, N, 19.17 per cent).

2-Phenyl-3-keto-5-methyl-dihydro-1:2:4-triazole (III).—The above compound (II) was heated on the water-bath with excess of 20% aqueous potash for 7-8 hours. The solution was cooled and acidified with acetic acid when there was evolution of carbon dioxide. The solid was crystallised from alcohol in brownish white needles, m.p. 210-212° (decomp). It is soluble in hydrochloric acid and precipitated by aqueous bicarbonate. (Found: N, 23.81. $C_9H_9ON_3$ requires N, 24.00 per cent).

2-Carboxyimino-4-acetylphenylhydrazone-1-phenylpyrazolone (IV).—The method of preparation is as with (I). The reaction product crystallised from hot water in colourless needles, m.p. 185-86° (decomp.). (Found: C, 61.25; H, 5.28; N, 19.95; M.W. by titration, 356. $C_{18}H_{17}O_3N_5$ requires C, 61.54; H, 4.84; N, 19.94 per cent. M.W., 351). It is readily soluble in bicarbonate solution and precipitated by acids. It does not give any azo-compound with ferric chloride and does not decolourise bromine water.

3-Carboxyimino-4-carbethoxy-pyrazolone (V).—The method of preparation is as with (I). The product was purified by precipitation

by acid from its solution in sodium bicarbonate and finally crystallised from dilute alcohol in beautiful colourless needles, m.p. 181°. [Found: N, 17'32; 17'34; H₂O, 10'78; M.W. (by titration), 240. C₇H₉O₃N₃, 1½H₂O requires N, 17'35; H₂O, 11'15 per cent. M.W., 242]. It does not yield any azo-compound with ferric chloride. When heated at its melting point for about 2 hours, it lost the water of crystallisation which was estimated.

3-Carboxyiminopyrazolone (VI).—The above compound (V, 3 g.) was treated with excess of 10% alcoholic potash and the clear solution heated on the water-bath for about half an hour when a voluminous precipitate slowly came out, which was kept overnight at room temperature. It was filtered, washed several times with alcohol and treated with dilute acetic acid when there was evolution of carbon dioxide. The clear solution was evaporated to dryness and the dried mass dissolved in cold water, when the brown solution, on standing for some time, gave a crystalline precipitate which further crystallised from water in brownish white prisms, m.p. above 300° (turning dark at 250°), yield 1 g. (Found: N, 23'41; M. W. by titration, 178. C₄H₅O₃N₃, 2H₂O requires N, 23'46 per cent. M. W., 179).

3-Carboxyimino-4-benzylidene-pyrazolone (VII).—An acetic acid solution of the above compound (VI, 1'8 g.) and benzaldehyde (1'1 g.) was heated under reflux for about an hour and diluted with water. The precipitated solid crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates. It softens and turns pink at 180° and slowly resinifies above 280°, yield 1'4 g. It is readily soluble in aqueous bicarbonate. (Found: N, 16'12. C₁₁H₉O₃N₃, 2H₂O requires N, 15'73 per cent).

3-Keto-5-diacetylmethyl-dihydro-1:2:4-triazole (VIII).—The method of preparation is as with (I). The reaction mixture was diluted with water until the solution was slightly turbid. On being allowed to cool slowly, the solution deposited a crystalline mass which crystallised from hot water in colourless slender needles, m. p. 70-71°. (Found: C, 45'62; H, 5'28; N, 22'68. C₇H₉O₃N₃ requires C, 45'90; H, 4'91; N, 22'95 per cent). It is insoluble in aqueous bicarbonate but readily soluble in alkali. It gives a red colouration with ferric chloride.

3-Keto-5-acetylmethyl-dihydro-1:2:4-triazole (IX).—The method of preparation is as with (II). The solid crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 228-230°. (Found: N, 30'05.

$C_5H_7O_2N_3$ requires N, 29.78 per cent). It is insoluble in aqueous bicarbonate but readily soluble in alkali.

Dicarbethoxythioacetylcarbamic acid and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide: Formation of 3-carboxyimino-5-keto-7-phenylimino-1:4-carbonyl-1:2:6-thioheptadiazine (X).—The method of procedure is the same as in the case of the previous compound (I). The reaction product crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m. p. 183° (decomp.). [Found: N, 18.44; S, 10.35; M. W. (by titration), 301. $C_{12}H_8O_4N_4S$ requires N, 18.42; S, 10.52 per cent. M. W., 304]. It is not desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury. It is soluble in bicarbonate solution and in moderately strong hydrochloric acid. It does not give any azo-compound with ferric chloride.

2-Dicarbethoxymethyl-benzimidazole (XI).—A glacial acetic acid solution of equimolecular proportions of *o*-phenylenediamine and dicarbethoxythioacetylcarbamic acid was heated under reflux till the evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen had ceased. On cooling, a crystalline mass at once came out which crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless slender needles, m. p. 218° . (Found: N, 10.28. $C_{14}H_{16}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.14 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali but soluble in concentrated hydrochloric acid. It does not respond to diazotisation and coupling with β -naphthol.

Hydrolysis of compound (XI): Formation of 2-methylbenzimidazole (XII).—A mixture of the above compound (5 g.) and 15% alcoholic potash (40 c. c.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath for about 5 hours and the solution was evaporated nearly to dryness on a water-bath. The aqueous solution of the pasty mass was acidified with acetic acid and evaporated to dryness. The dried mass was finely powdered and triturated with cold water, when an insoluble white powder was obtained which crystallised from hot water in colourless needles, m. p. $169-70^\circ$ (mixed m. p. with 2-methyl-benzimidazole, Hübner, *loc. cit.*), yield 0.8 g. (Found: N, 21.42. $C_8H_8N_2$ requires N, 21.21 per cent).

2-Diacetylmethyl-benzimidazole (XIII).—An alcoholic solution of equimolecular proportions of *o*-phenylenediamine and diacetylthioacetocarbamic acid was heated under reflux till the evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen had ceased. The solution was cooled and diluted with water when a viscous semi-solid mass was obtained. It was purified by dissolving in alcohol and precipitation by adding large quantity of

ether. The solid was finally crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether in colourless needles, m.p. 138-39°. (Found : C, 66.89 ; H, 6.01. N, 13.19. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires C, 66.66 ; H, 5.55 ; N, 12.96 per cent). It does not condense with phenyl isocyanate, showing thereby the absence of any free amino group.

The *hydrochloride* was obtained by dissolving the above compound in hydrochloric acid and evaporating the solution. The solid crystallised from water acidulated with a few drops of hydrochloric acid in colourless shining rectangular plates, m. p. 243-244° (decomp. ; producing a fine green colouration). (Found : N, 10.73. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2$, HCl requires N, 11.11 per cent). On treatment with aqueous bicarbonate, it yielded the original compound (XIV).

2-Dicarbethoxymethyl-dihydro-imidazole (XIV).—The method of preparation is as with (XI). The product crystallised from water in colourless slender needles, m. p. 100-101°. It is soluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitated by alkali. It does not condense with phenyl isocyanate, showing thereby the absence of any free amino group. (Found : N, 12.41. $C_{10}H_{16}O_4N_2$ requires N, 12.28 per cent).

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